

Trajectory Tracking of a Nonholonomic Mobile Robot With Parametric and Nonparametric Uncertainties: A Proposed Neural Control

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Abstract: In this paper, a trajectory tracking control for a nonholonomic mobile robot by the integration of a kinematic neural controller (KNC) and a torque neural controller (TNC) is proposed, where both the kinematic and dynamic models contains parametric and nonparametric uncertainties. The proposed neural controller (PNC) is constituted of the KNC and the TNC, and designed by use of a modeling technique of Gaussian radial basis function neural networks (RBFNNs). The KNC is applied to compensate the parametric uncertainties of the mobile robot kinematics. The TNC, based on the sliding mode theory, is constituted of a dynamic neural controller (DNC) and a robust neural compensator (RNC), and applied to compensate the mobile robot dynamics, significant uncertainties, bounded unknown disturbances, neural network modeling errors, influence of payload, and unknown kinematic parameters. To alleviate the problems met in practical implementation using classical sliding mode controllers and to eliminate the chattering phenomenon is used the RNC of the TNC, which is nonlinear and continuous, in lieu of the discontinuous part of the control signals present in classical forms. Also, the PNC neither requires the knowledge of the mobile robot kinematics and dynamics nor the time-consuming training process. Stability analysis and convergence of tracking errors to zero as well as the learning algorithms for weights are guaranteed with basis on Lyapunov method. Simulations results are provided to show the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

Key-Words: mobile robot, trajectory tracking, kinematic control, dynamic control, neural networks, Lyapunov theory

1. INTRODUCTION

Besides the stabilization problem of the nonholonomic systems, the tracking control problem is more

interesting in practice. Based on whether the system is described by a kinematic model or a dynamic model, the tracking control problem is classified as either a kinematic or a dynamic tracking control problem. The kinematic tracking control problem has been studied in last two decades [1],[2]. The dynamic tracking-control problem of the nonholonomic system has received attention, because most practical nonholonomic mechanical systems are dynamic systems and have uncertainties [3],[4]. For mobile robot, its motion is eventually being driving by force or torque. It is more suitable to design a controller that integrates the nonholonomic kinematics controller with the dynamic model of the mobile robot [5],[6],[7].

Moreover, it is impossible to get the exact kinematic parameters and the dynamics of the robot in reality. How to design the nonholonomic kinematic controller and dynamic controller under these conditions is still an open question. In the literature, most of the results on the dynamic tracking problem of nonholonomic systems are proposed based on the assumption that the kinematics of the system is exactly known or by selecting a special control target, i.e. the forward velocity and the angular velocity of the robot, to avoid this problem, and there are only uncertainties in the dynamics of the system. However, in practice, there are uncertainties in both kinematics and dynamics.

As there are few works [8], [9], [10] dealing of both the unknown dynamics and unknown kinematics, this paper describes the PNC that addresses the problem of integration of the KNC and the TNC (based on the sliding mode theory), considering the presence of parametric and nonparametric uncertainties in the kinematic and dynamic models.

Due to robustness properties against uncertainties, modeling imprecision and disturbances, sliding mode control has become very popular and enjoys a wide variety of applications areas [11]. Other advantage of using sliding mode control is the fast response good transient performance. However, this control scheme has important drawbacks limiting its practical applicability, such as chattering and large control

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authority. Therefore it deteriorates the system performance.

Recently, much research works have been done to use softcomputing methodologies such as artificial neural networks in order to improve the performance and alleviate the problem met in practical implementation of sliding mode controllers [12],[13].

A novel kinematics/dynamics control scheme that integrates a velocity controller with an adaptive neuron and a sliding mode controller for the tracking control of a mobile robot is proposed in [14]. But, there is not a stability analysis and convergence of the closed-loop system of a more solid form.

A control scheme for mobile robots, which includes a velocity controller based on backstepping techniques and a torque controller based on improved radial basis function neural networks (IRBFNN) is presented in [15]. The torque control strategy is derived from sliding mode control, but it depends excessively of the mobile robots dynamics. Moreover, the control algorithms are complex and computationally expensive. Also, there are still not established proofs and formal criteria of stability and convergence of the closed-loop system using IRBFNN.

In this paper, the RBFNN is applied to control a kinematic and dynamic systems, since the structure of an RFBNN is simpler that a multi-layer perceptron (MLP), the learning rate of RBFNN is generally faster than a MLP, and a RBFNN is mathematically tractable easily [16]. Differently from other investigations with mobile robots [6],[7],[8],[9],[10],[15], the contributions are:

- The implementation of the PNC (KNC plus TNC) is based on the partitioning of the RBFNN into several smaller subnets in order to obtain more efficient computation;

- An neural sliding mode controller as RNC of the TNC is used in the replacement of the discontinuous parts of the classical sliding mode controller to avoid the chattering as well as to suppress the neural network modeling errors, bounded unknown disturbances, influence of payload, and unknown kinematic parameters;

- The PNC neither requires the knowledge of the mobile robot kinematics and dynamics nor the time-consuming training process;

- The stability analysis and convergence of the mobile robot control system, and the learning algorithms for weights are proved by using Lyapunov theory.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the approach about the nonholonomic mobile robots kinematics and dynamics, and the neural networks modeling. Section 3 describes the PNC for a reference

trajectory tracking. Section 4 shows the simulations results, and the Section 5 presents the conclusions.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 Kinematics and Dynamics of a Mobile Robot

A typical example of a nonholonomic mobile robot is shown in Fig. 2.1. The robot has two driving wheels mounted on the same axis and a free front wheel. The two driving wheels are independently driven by two actuators to achieve the motion and orientation. The position of the mobile robot in the Cartesian frame X, O, Y can be described by a vector \bar{O}_n , and the orientation between mobile robot base frame X_n, n, Y_n and the Cartesian frame.

Fig. 2.1. Model of a nonholonomic mobile robot.

Disregarding surface friction $F(\dot{q})$ and $G(q)=0$, the dynamics of a nonholonomic mobile robot (Fig. 2.1) subject to m constraints can be expressed as [5]:

$$H(q)\ddot{q} + C(q, \dot{q})\dot{q} + \tau_d = B(q)\tau + A^T(q)\lambda \tag{2.1}$$

where $H(q)$ is an $n \times n$ symmetric, positive definite inertia matrix; $C(q, \dot{q})$ is the $n \times n$ centripetal and Coriolis matrix; τ_d denotes the bounded unknown disturbances including unstructured and unmodeled dynamics; $B(q)$ is the $n \times r$ input transformation matrix; τ is the $r \times 1$ input vector; $A(q)$ is the $m \times n$ Jacobian matrix associated with the constraints; λ is the $m \times 1$ constraints force vector; and $q \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$ is the configuration of the robot that can be described by five generalized coordinates:

$$q = [x, y, \theta, \phi_r, \phi_l] \tag{2.2}$$

where (x, y) are the coordinates of n , θ is the orientation angle of the mobile robot, and (ϕ_r, ϕ_l) are the angles of the right and left driving wheels.

On the condition of pure rolling and non-slipping, the mobile robot can only move in direction normal to the driving wheels axis. Therefore, the nonholonomic constraint of the mobile robot can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{y} \cos(\theta) - \dot{x} \sin(\theta) - d\dot{\theta} &= 0 \\ \dot{x} \cos(\theta) + \dot{y} \sin(\theta) + R\dot{\theta} &= r\dot{\phi}_r = r\nu_r, \\ \dot{x} \cos(\theta) + \dot{y} \sin(\theta) - R\dot{\theta} &= r\dot{\phi}_l = r\nu_l, \end{aligned} \tag{2.3}$$

Thus, the kinematic constraints can be written as:

$$A(q)\dot{q} = 0 \tag{2.4}$$

with:

$$A(q) = \begin{bmatrix} \sin(\theta) & -\cos(\theta) & d & 0 & 0 \\ \cos(\theta) & \sin(\theta) & R & -r & 0 \\ \cos(\theta) & \sin(\theta) & -R & 0 & -r \end{bmatrix} \tag{2.5}$$

Let $S(q)$ be a $n-m$ full rank matrix made up by a set of smooth and linearly independent vector spanning the null space of $A(q)$, i.e.,

$$A(q)S(q) = 0 \tag{2.6}$$

with:

$$S(q) = \begin{bmatrix} (r/2R)(R \cos(\theta) - d \sin(\theta)) & (r/2R)(R \cos(\theta) + d \sin(\theta)) \\ (r/2R)(R \sin(\theta) + d \cos(\theta)) & (r/2R)(R \sin(\theta) - d \cos(\theta)) \\ (r/2R) & -(r/2R) \\ 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \tag{2.7}$$

Since the constrained velocity is always in the null space of $A(q)$, from (2.4) and (2.6), it is possible to find $n-m$ velocities $v(t)$, such that :

$$\dot{q} = S(q)v(t) \tag{2.8}$$

where $v(t) = [v_r \ v_l]^T$ represent the angular velocities of right and left wheels.

Using (2.8) and multiplying $S^T(q)$ on (2.1), the mobile robot dynamics in (2.1) can be transformed into a more appropriated representation for the control purpose as:

$$\bar{H}(q)\ddot{v} + \bar{C}(q, \dot{q})\dot{v} + \bar{\tau}_d = \bar{B}\tau = \bar{\tau} \tag{2.9}$$

with:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{H}(q) &= S^T H S = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{H}_{11} & \bar{H}_{12} \\ \bar{H}_{21} & \bar{H}_{22} \end{bmatrix} \\ \bar{H}_{11} &= (r^2/4R^2)(md^2 + 2m_c d^2 + mR^2 + I) + I_w \\ \bar{H}_{12} &= -(r^2/4R^2)(md^2 + 2m_c d^2 - mR^2 + I) \\ \bar{H}_{21} &= -(r^2/4R^2)(md^2 + 2m_c d^2 - mR^2 + I) \\ \bar{H}_{22} &= (r^2/4R^2)(md^2 + 2m_c d^2 + mR^2 + I) + I_w \\ \bar{C}(q, \dot{q}) &= S^T (HS + CS) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & (r^2 d/2R)(m + m_c)\dot{\theta} \\ -(r^2 d/2R)(m + m_c)\dot{\theta} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ \bar{B}(q) &= S^T B = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \tag{2.10}$$

where $\tau = [\tau_r \ \tau_l]^T$ is the torque applied on the right and left wheel; r is the radius of the wheel; $2R$ is the length of the axis between the wheels of the mobile robot; $m = m_c + 2m_w$; $I = m_c d^2 + 2m_w((2R)^2 + d^2) + I_c + 2I_m$; d is the distance from n to c ; m_c is the mass of the robot

platform; m_w is the mass of each driving wheel plus the rotor of its motor; I_c , I_w , and I_m are the moment of inertia of the platform about the vertical axis through n , the wheel with the actuator about the wheel axis, and the wheel with the actuator about the wheel diameter, respectively.

In (2.9), it should be noted that the pattern properties of boundedness of $\bar{H}(q)$, bounded norm of the $\bar{C}(q, \dot{q})$ and $\bar{\tau}_d$, and of skew-symmetry ($\bar{H} - 2\bar{C}$) are considered in the stability analysis of the control system.

Assumption 1: $\bar{B}(q)$ does not include unknown parameters and is nonsingular.

Assumption 1 is easily relaxed by the existing adaptive control technique, if $\bar{B}(q)$ is constant and the sign of each elements is known.

2.2 Neural Networks Modeling

Based on (2.9), it can be verified that $\bar{H}(q)$ is function of q only, and $\bar{C}(q, \dot{q}) = \bar{C}(z)$ is a function of q and \dot{q} , thus, static neural networks and dynamic neural networks are enough to model them, respectively. Therefore, the stability of the neural networks can be analyzed, where matrix Ge-Lee (GL) [17], defined by $\{.\}$, and its product operator \bullet are used. The ordinary matrix and vector are denoted by $[.]$.

Foregrounded in (2.9), the matrices $\bar{H}(q)$ and $\bar{C}(q, \dot{q})$ of the mobile robot dynamics can be expressed by:

$$\bar{H}(q) = \{W_{\bar{H}}\} \bullet \{e_{\bar{H}}(q)\} + E_{\bar{H}}(q), \quad \bar{C}(q, \dot{q}) = \{W_{\bar{C}}\} \bullet \{e_{\bar{C}}(z)\} + E_{\bar{C}}(z) \tag{2.11}$$

where $\{W_{\bar{H}}\}$, $\{e_{\bar{H}}(q)\}$, $\{W_{\bar{C}}\}$, and $\{e_{\bar{C}}(z)\}$ are GL matrices, and their respective elements are $W_{\bar{H}_{ij}}$, $e_{\bar{H}_{ij}}(q)$, $W_{\bar{C}_{ij}}$, and $e_{\bar{C}_{ij}}(z)$. $E_{\bar{H}}(q) \in R^{n \times n}$ and $E_{\bar{C}}(z) \in R^{n \times n}$ are matrices, and their modeling error elements $\varepsilon_{\bar{H}_{ij}}(q)$ and $\varepsilon_{\bar{C}_{ij}}(z)$, respectively.

It is important to emphasize that a $P(.)$ vector can be modeled with static neural networks, since it is a function of a variable only. Thus, $P(.)$ results in:

$$P(.) = \{W_P\} \bullet \{e_P(.)\} + E_P(.) \tag{2.12}$$

where $\{W_P\}$ and $\{e_P(.)\}$ are GL vectors, and their respective elements are W_{P_k} and $e_{P_k}(.)$. $E_P(.) \in R^n$ is a vector, and their modeling error elements $\varepsilon_{P_k}(.)$.

3. CONTROL DESIGN - TRAJECTORY TRACKING

In this section, the PNC (KNC plus TNC) is designed for the kinematic model and the dynamic model. The KNC for the kinematic part, (2.8), is based on the modifying the method proposed by [1]. The TNC for the dynamic part, (2.9), that consists of a DNC and a

RNC, is based on the sliding mode theory.

3.1 Neural Control of the Kinematic Model

For the given mobile robot in Fig. 2.1, both the wheel mass and moment of inertia are considered in the dynamic model. Therefore, the angular velocity of the wheel could be selected as the kinematic control targets. This approach is more realistic than most other models where the linear velocity and the orientation angular velocity of the mobile robot are selected as the control targets because the torques of the actuator are actually applied directly on the wheel and control the angular velocity of the wheels. Assume the linear velocity and the orientation angular velocity of the mobile robot at point n are v_L and ω_A , therefore,

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_r \\ v_l \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (d/r)d & (Rd/r)d \\ (d/r)d & -(Rd/r)d \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_L \\ \omega_A \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (1/r) & (R/r) \\ (1/r) & -(R/r) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_L \\ \omega_A \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\dot{q} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{\theta} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & -d \sin(\theta) \\ \sin(\theta) & d \cos(\theta) \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_L \\ \omega_A \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.1)$$

For the mobile robot, the controller design problem can be described as: given the reference position $q_r(t)$ and the velocity $\dot{q}_r(t)$, design control law for the actuator torques, which drive the mobile robot to move, so the mobile robot velocity tracking a smooth velocity control input and the reference position. Let velocity and position of a reference robot are given as:

$$q_r = [x_d \ y_d \ \theta_d]^T, \ v_{r,f} = [v_d \ \omega_d]^T$$

$$\dot{x}_r = v_d \cos(\theta_d), \ \dot{y}_r = v_d \sin(\theta_d), \ \dot{\theta}_r = \omega_d \quad (3.2)$$

where $v_d > 0$ for all t is the reference linear velocity and ω_d is the reference angular velocity. Thus, the position tracking error vector is expressed in the basis of a frame linked to the mobile robot platform as:

$$e_q = \begin{bmatrix} e_1 \\ e_2 \\ e_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & \sin(\theta) & 0 \\ -\sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_d - x \\ y_d - y \\ \theta_d - \theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.3)$$

The position error dynamics can be obtained from the time derivative of (3.3) as:

$$\dot{e}_q = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{e}_1 \\ \dot{e}_2 \\ \dot{e}_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \omega_A e_2 - v_L + v_d \cos(e_3) \\ -\omega_A e_1 + v_d \sin(e_3) \\ \omega_d - \omega_A \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} v_L + \begin{bmatrix} e_2 \\ -e_1 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix} \omega_A + \begin{bmatrix} v_d \cos(e_3) \\ v_d \sin(e_3) \\ \omega_d \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.4)$$

An selected smooth velocity input v_s , that achieves tracking for (2.8), is given by [1]:

$$v_s = \begin{bmatrix} v_f \\ \omega_f \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v_d \cos(e_3) + k_1 e_1 \\ \omega_d + k_2 v_d e_2 + k_3 v_d \sin(e_3) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.5)$$

where k_1, k_2 and k_3 are positive parameters.

By using (3.1), the Eq. (3.4) can also be expressed using wheel angular velocity as:

$$\dot{e}_q = \begin{bmatrix} -(r/2) + (r/2R)e_2 \\ -(r/2R)e_1 \\ -(r/2R) \end{bmatrix} v_r + \begin{bmatrix} -(r/2) - (r/2R)e_2 \\ (r/2R)e_1 \\ (r/2R) \end{bmatrix} v_l + \begin{bmatrix} v_d \cos(e_3) \\ v_d \sin(e_3) \\ \omega_d \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.6)$$

From kinematics, (2.8), if the parameters, r, R and d , are unknown, the kinematic control targets, angular velocity of the wheels, can not be obtained from the selected velocity input because of the relationship (3.1) between v_L, ω_A and v_r, v_l . But it is possible to use the estimates of these parameters in (3.1) and design learning algorithm for the neural controller to learn these parameters. Assume:

$$a_1 = (d/r)d = (1/r), \ b_1 = (Rd/r)d = (R/r) \quad (3.7)$$

Replacing the linear and angular velocities in (3.1) with (3.5), it becomes:

$$v_c = \begin{bmatrix} v_{c1} \\ v_{c2} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v_r \\ v_l \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{a}_1 & \hat{b}_1 \\ \hat{a}_1 & -\hat{b}_1 \end{bmatrix} v_f = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{a}_1 \\ \hat{a}_1 \end{bmatrix} v_f + \begin{bmatrix} \hat{b}_1 \\ -\hat{b}_1 \end{bmatrix} \omega_f =$$

$$v_c = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 - \tilde{a}_1 & b_1 - \tilde{b}_1 \\ a_1 - \tilde{a}_1 & -(b_1 - \tilde{b}_1) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_f \\ \omega_f \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.8)$$

where \hat{a}_1 and \hat{b}_1 are the estimates of a_1 and b_1 , $\tilde{a}_1 = a_1 - \hat{a}_1$ and $\tilde{b}_1 = b_1 - \hat{b}_1$ are the estimated errors respectively; and the wheel angular velocity is defined as the velocity control input v_c .

Using (2.12), assume that the \hat{A} and \hat{B} vectors of (3.8) can be modeled with static neural networks as:

$$v_c = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{W}_{A1}^T \xi_{A1}(a_1) \\ \hat{W}_{A2}^T \xi_{A2}(a_1) \end{bmatrix} v_f + \begin{bmatrix} \hat{W}_{B1}^T \xi_{B1}(b_1) \\ \hat{W}_{B2}^T \xi_{B2}(b_1) \end{bmatrix} \omega_f = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{W}_{A1}^T \xi_{A1}(a_1) \\ \hat{W}_{A1}^T \xi_{A1}(a_1) \end{bmatrix} v_f + \begin{bmatrix} \hat{W}_{B1}^T \xi_{B1}(b_1) \\ -\hat{W}_{B1}^T \xi_{B1}(b_1) \end{bmatrix} \omega_f$$

$$v_c = \begin{bmatrix} (W_{A1}^T - \tilde{W}_{A1}^T) \xi_{A1}(a_1) & (W_{B1}^T - \tilde{W}_{B1}^T) \xi_{B1}(b_1) \\ (W_{A1}^T - \tilde{W}_{A1}^T) \xi_{A1}(a_1) & -(W_{B1}^T - \tilde{W}_{B1}^T) \xi_{B1}(b_1) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_f \\ \omega_f \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.9)$$

since $\hat{W}_{A1}^T \xi_{A1}(a_1) = \hat{W}_{A2}^T \xi_{A2}(a_1)$, $\hat{W}_{B2}^T \xi_{B2}(b_1) = -\hat{W}_{B1}^T \xi_{B1}(b_1)$, and $W^T \xi(\cdot)$ is an optimal static neural network with $\varepsilon(\cdot) = 0$.

Substituting (3.9) in (3.6), it becomes:

$$\dot{e}_q = (1 - (\tilde{W}_{A1}^T \xi_{A1}(a_1) / W_{A1}^T \xi_{A1}(a_1))) v_f \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} +$$

$$+ (1 - (\tilde{W}_{B1}^T \xi_{B1}(b_1) / W_{B1}^T \xi_{B1}(b_1))) \omega_f \begin{bmatrix} e_2 \\ -e_1 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} v_d \cos(e_3) \\ v_d \sin(e_3) \\ \omega_d \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.10)$$

The velocity tracking error can be defined as:

$$e_c = v_r - v = \begin{bmatrix} v_{c1} - v_r \\ v_{c2} - v_l \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.11)$$

Choosing the Lyapunov function candidate in the form:

$$V_1 = (1/2)(e_1^2 + e_2^2 + 2((1 - \cos(e_3))/k_2)) + ((\tilde{W}_{A1}^T \xi_{A1}(a_1))^2 / (\gamma_1 \tilde{W}_{A1}^T \xi_{A1}(a_1))) + ((\tilde{W}_{B1}^T \xi_{B1}(b_1))^2 / (\gamma_2 \tilde{W}_{B1}^T \xi_{B1}(b_1))) \quad (3.12)$$

with $\gamma_1 > 0, \gamma_2 > 0$. Apparently, $V_1 \geq 0$, and $V_1 = 0$ if only if $e_q = 0, \tilde{W}_{A1}^T \xi_{A1}(a_1) = 0$, and $\tilde{W}_{B1}^T \xi_{B1}(b_1) = 0$.

Differentiating (3.12), substituting (3.10) and using (3.5), \dot{V}_1 stays:

$$\dot{V}_1 = -k_2 e_1^2 - ((k_3 v_d \sin^2(e_3))/k_2) + ((\tilde{W}_{A1}^T \xi_{A1}(a_1)) / (\gamma_1 \tilde{W}_{A1}^T \xi_{A1}(a_1))) (\gamma_1 e_1 v_f - \dot{\tilde{W}}_{A1}^T \xi_{A1}(a_1)) + ((\tilde{W}_{B1}^T \xi_{B1}(b_1)) / (\gamma_2 \tilde{W}_{B1}^T \xi_{B1}(b_1))) ((\gamma_2 \sin(e_3))/k_2) \omega_f - \dot{\tilde{W}}_{B1}^T \xi_{B1}(b_1) \quad (3.13)$$

Now, the parameter learning rules are chosen as:

$$\dot{\tilde{W}}_{A1} = \gamma_1 e_1 v_f (\xi_{A1}^+(a_1))^T, \quad \dot{\tilde{W}}_{B1} = ((\gamma_2 \sin(e_3))/k_2) \omega_f (\xi_{B1}^+(b_1))^T \quad (3.14)$$

where $\xi^+(\cdot)$ is a pseudoinverse matrix.

Substituting (3.14) in (3.13), one obtain:

$$\dot{V}_1 = -k_1 e_1^2 - ((k_3 v_d \sin^2(e_3))/k_2) \quad (3.15)$$

Apparently, $\dot{V}_1 \leq 0, \dot{V}_1 = 0$ if only if, $e_1 = 0$ and $e_3 = 0$. From (3.10), \dot{e}_1 and \dot{e}_3 are bounded since $\tilde{W}_{A1}^T \xi_{A1}(a_1)$ and $\tilde{W}_{B1}^T \xi_{B1}(b_1)$ are bounded. After all, \dot{V}_1 is bounded. Barbalat's lemma shows that $\dot{V}_1 \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$, that is, by $e_1 \rightarrow 0, e_3 \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$, one can deduce that $\|e_q\|$ and $\|\dot{e}_q\|$ are bounded. Moreover, (3.5) and (3.8)-(3.9) show that $v_{c1} = v_r$ and $v_{c2} = v_l$ are bounded.

3.2 Neural Control of the Dynamic Model

One may require sliding conditions of the form

$$(1/2)(d/dt)(s^T s) \leq -\eta \sum_{k=1}^n |s_k|, \quad \eta > 0, \text{ with the vector } s \text{ defined as:}$$

$$s = v_r - v = e_c + \Lambda \int_0^t e_c dt \quad (3.16)$$

where $\Lambda^T = \Lambda > 0$ is a symmetric diagonal positive definite matrix, and $\int_0^t e_c dt$ is a auxiliary position tracking error, which does not reflect the position tracking error e_q directly, besides not having physical meaning. One may interpret s of (3.16) as a filtered tracking error term, where $v_r = v_r + \Lambda \int_0^t e_c dt$ is the reference velocity vector.

In the presence of bounded unknown disturbances $\bar{\tau}_d$, energy conservation can be written as

$(1/2)(d/dt)(v^T \bar{H}(q)v) = v^T (\bar{\tau} - \bar{\tau}_d)$, and differentiating the left hand side explicitly as well as expanding the term $\bar{H}(q)\dot{v}$ using the system dynamics, (2.9), one conclude, after simplification of the input terms $(\bar{\tau} - \bar{\tau}_d)$, that for all $v, v^T (\bar{H}(q) - 2\bar{C}(q, \dot{q}))v = 0$. This result confirms that the matrix $\bar{H}(q) - 2\bar{C}(q, \dot{q})$ is skew-symmetric.

With this formalization of energy conservation, one can choose the Lyapunov function as follows:

$$V_2 = (1/2)(s^T \bar{H}(q)s + \sum_{k=1}^n \tilde{W}_{Hk}^T \Gamma_{Hk}^{-1} \tilde{W}_{Hk} + \sum_{k=1}^n \tilde{W}_{Ck}^T \Gamma_{Ck}^{-1} \tilde{W}_{Ck} + \sum_{k=1}^n \tilde{W}_{Pk}^T \Gamma_{Pk}^{-1} \tilde{W}_{Pk}) + \left(\int_0^t e_c dt \right)^T \Lambda \int_0^t e_c dt \quad (3.17)$$

where Γ_k are dimensional compatible symmetric positive definite matrices, and $\{\tilde{W}_k\} = \{\tilde{W}_k\} - \{\hat{W}_k\}$. Clearly, $V_2 \geq 0$, and $V_2 = 0$ if only if $\int_0^t e_c dt = 0, s = 0, \{\tilde{W}_{Hk}\} = 0, \{\tilde{W}_{Ck}\} = 0$, and $\{\tilde{W}_{Pk}\} = 0$.

Differentiating (3.17), recall that $v = v_r - s$ of (3.16), $\dot{s} = \dot{v}_r - \dot{v}$, $\{\dot{\tilde{W}}_k\} = -\{\dot{\hat{W}}_k\}$, and substituting the term $\bar{H}(q)\dot{v}$ from the system dynamics, (2.9), \dot{V}_2 results in:

$$\dot{V}_2 = s^T (\bar{H}(q)\dot{v}_r + \bar{C}(q, \dot{q})v_r + \bar{\tau}_d - \bar{\tau}) - \sum_{k=1}^n \tilde{W}_{Hk}^T \Gamma_{Hk}^{-1} \dot{\tilde{W}}_{Hk} - \sum_{k=1}^n \tilde{W}_{Ck}^T \Gamma_{Ck}^{-1} \dot{\tilde{W}}_{Ck} - \sum_{k=1}^n \tilde{W}_{Pk}^T \Gamma_{Pk}^{-1} \dot{\tilde{W}}_{Pk} + 2e_c^T \Lambda \int_0^t e_c dt \quad (3.18)$$

where the skew symmetry property of $\bar{H}(q) - 2\bar{C}(q, \dot{q})$ has been used to eliminate the term $(1/2)s^T \bar{H}(q)s$.

One define the control input to be of the form:

$$\bar{\tau} = \hat{\tau} - \gamma = \hat{H}(q)\dot{v}_r + \hat{C}(q, \dot{q})v_r - \gamma = \underbrace{\left[\hat{W}_{Hk}^T \cdot \xi_{Hk}(q) \right]}_{DNC} \dot{v}_r + \underbrace{\left[\hat{W}_{Ck}^T \cdot \xi_{Ck}(z) \right]}_{DNC} v_r - \gamma \quad (3.19)$$

where $\{\hat{W}_{Hk}\}$, and $\{\hat{W}_{Ck}\}$ represent estimates of true parameters of weights matrices $\{W_{Hk}\}$, and $\{W_{Ck}\}$ of (2.11), and γ is the constant plus proportional rate reaching law with the aim of compensating for the bounded unknown disturbances [18],[19], which it is defined:

$$\gamma = -G \text{sgn}(s) - (Q + I_n)s \quad (3.20)$$

where $G^T = G > 0, (Q + I_n)^T = (Q + I_n) > 0$, and I_n is identity matrix.

It is necessary to emphasize that in (3.20) the discontinuous control signal will cause a significant problem of chattering, which will excite the high frequencies dynamics of nonlinear system. As that is highly undesirable, to eliminate chattering entirely, is

proposed a RBFNN, (2.12), as continuous approximation of $G_{sgn(s)}$ in γ , (3.20). Then,

$$\gamma = -\hat{P} - (Q + I_n)s = - \underbrace{\left[\tilde{W}_P^T \cdot \xi_P(s) \right]}_{RNC} - (Q + I_n)s \quad (3.21)$$

with $\hat{P}(s)$ being an $n \times 1$ vector in which \hat{p}_k is the output of the i -th RBFNN. Thus, \dot{v}_2 becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{v}_2 = & s^T \left[\tilde{W}_H^T \cdot \xi_H(q) \right] \dot{v}_r + s^T \left[\tilde{W}_C^T \cdot \xi_C(z) \right] \dot{v}_r + s^T \bar{r}_d + s^T E - \\ & - s^T \left[\tilde{W}_P^T \cdot \xi_P(s) \right] - s^T (Q + I_n)s - \sum_{k=1}^n \tilde{W}_{Hk}^T \Gamma_{Hk}^{-1} \dot{\tilde{W}}_{Hk} - \\ & - \sum_{k=1}^n \tilde{W}_{Ck}^T \Gamma_{Ck}^{-1} \dot{\tilde{W}}_{Ck} - \sum_{k=1}^n \tilde{W}_{Pk}^T \Gamma_{Pk}^{-1} \dot{\tilde{W}}_{Pk} + 2e_c^T \Lambda \int_0^t e_c dt \end{aligned} \quad (3.22)$$

where $E = E_H(q)\dot{v}_r + E_C(z)\dot{v}_r$, define the neural network modeling errors. Recall that:

$$\begin{aligned} s^T \left[\tilde{W}_H^T \cdot \xi_H(q) \right] \dot{v}_r &= \sum_{k=1}^n \tilde{W}_{Hk}^T \cdot \xi_{Hk}(q) \dot{v}_r s_k, \\ s^T \left[\tilde{W}_C^T \cdot \xi_C(z) \right] \dot{v}_r &= \sum_{k=1}^n \tilde{W}_{Ck}^T \cdot \xi_{Ck}(z) \dot{v}_r s_k, \\ s^T \left[\tilde{W}_P^T \cdot \xi_P(s) \right] &= \sum_{k=1}^n \tilde{W}_{Pk}^T \cdot \xi_{Pk}(s) \dot{v}_r s_k, \end{aligned}$$

and choosing the learning laws of neural networks as:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\tilde{W}}_{Hk} &= \Gamma_{Hk} \cdot \xi_{Hk}(q) \dot{v}_r s_k, \quad \dot{\tilde{W}}_{Ck} = \Gamma_{Ck} \cdot \xi_{Ck}(z) \dot{v}_r s_k, \\ \dot{\tilde{W}}_{Pk} &= \Gamma_{Pk} \cdot \xi_{Pk}(s) \dot{v}_r s_k \end{aligned} \quad (3.23)$$

and substituting (3.23) into (3.22), \dot{v}_2 results in:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{v}_2 \leq & \|s\| \|\bar{r}_d\| + \|s\| \|E\| - \sum_{k=1}^n \tilde{W}_{Pk}^T \cdot \xi_{Pk}(s) \dot{v}_r s_k - \\ & - Q_{min} \|s\|^2 - s^T I_n s + 2e_c^T \Lambda \int_0^t e_c dt \end{aligned} \quad (3.24)$$

with Q_{min} being the minimum singular values of Q .

Assuming that $\|\bar{r}_d\| = \sum_{k=1}^n |\bar{r}_{dk}| \leq b_d$, and $\|E\| = \sum_{k=1}^n |E_k| \leq e_{NN}$, one obtain:

$$\dot{v}_2 \leq -e_c^T e_c - \left(\int_0^t e_c dt \right)^T \Lambda^T \Lambda \int_0^t e_c dt - \sum_{k=1}^n Q_k |s_k|^2 + \sum_{k=1}^n |\Delta f_k - p_k| |s_k| \quad (3.25)$$

with $p_k = \tilde{W}_{Pk}^T \cdot \xi_{Pk}(s)$ being the optimal compensation for $\Delta f_k = \bar{r}_{dk} + E_k + \varphi_k$. According to the property of universal approximation of RBFNN, there exists $\psi_k > 0$ satisfying $|\Delta f_k - p_k| \leq \psi_k$, where ψ_k is arbitrary and can be chosen as small as possible. Assuming that $\psi_k \leq \beta_k |s_k|$ with $0 < \beta_k < 1$, one obtain $|\Delta f_k - p_k| |s_k| \leq \beta_k |s_k|^2 = \beta_k s_k^2$, therefore, \dot{v}_2 stays:

$$\dot{v}_2 \leq -e_c^T e_c - \left(\int_0^t e_c dt \right)^T \Lambda^T \Lambda \int_0^t e_c dt - \sum_{k=1}^n (Q_k - \beta_k) |s_k|^2 \quad (3.26)$$

Because of $Q_k > \beta_k$, \dot{v}_2 is guaranteed negative.

3.3 Stability Analysis and Convergence

To ensure that the global system is stable, the Lyapunov function candidate is given as:

$$V = V_1 + V_2 \quad (3.27)$$

where V_1 and V_2 refers to (3.12) and (3.17) respectively. Moreover, $V \geq 0$, and $V = 0$ if only if $e_q = 0$, $\tilde{W}_{d1}^T \xi_{d1}(a_1) = 0$, and $\tilde{W}_{d1}^T \xi_{d1}(b_1) = 0$, $\int_0^t e_c dt = 0$, $s = 0$, $\tilde{W}_H^T = 0$, $\tilde{W}_C^T = 0$, and $\tilde{W}_P^T = 0$.

Differentiating V , it becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V} \leq & -k_1 e_1^2 - ((k_3 v_d \sin^2(e_3)) / k_2) - e_c^T e_c - \\ & - \left(\int_0^t e_c dt \right)^T \Lambda^T \Lambda \int_0^t e_c dt - \sum_{k=1}^n (Q_k - \beta_k) |s_k|^2 \end{aligned} \quad (3.28)$$

being that $\Lambda^T \Lambda = \mu$, and μ_{min} are minimum singular values of μ . Apparently, $\dot{V} \leq 0$, $\dot{V} = 0$ if only if, $e_1 = 0$, $e_3 = 0$, $e_c = 0$, $\int_0^t e_c dt = 0$, $s = 0$, and $Q_k > \beta_k$. According to a standard Lyapunov theory and Barbalat's lemma, the control system is asymptotically stable and the error $e = [e_q^T \ e_c^T]^T$ is bounded. By $[e_1 \ e_3]^T \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$, one can deduce that $\|e_q\|$ and $\|e_c\|$ are bounded. From (16), one obtain:

$$\omega_d - \omega_A = 0 \quad (3.29)$$

and considering $e_c = 0$ in (3.11), and using (3.5), results in:

$$k_2 v_d e_2 = 0 \quad (3.30)$$

By assumption $v_d \geq 0$, then $e_2 \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$. Therefore, the equilibrium point $e = [e_q^T \ e_c^T]^T = 0$ is uniformly asymptotically stable.

In summary, since \dot{v}_1 and \dot{v}_2 are guaranteed to be negative, then \dot{v} is also guaranteed negative. According to a standard Lyapunov theory and Barbalat lemma, all signals $\|e_q\|$, $\|e_c\|$, $\tilde{W}_{d1}^T \xi_{d1}(a_1)$, $\tilde{W}_{d1}^T \xi_{d1}(b_1)$, $\left\| \int_0^t e_c dt \right\|$, $\|s\|$, $\{\tilde{W}_H^T\}$, $\{\tilde{W}_C^T\}$, and $\{\tilde{W}_P^T\}$ are bounded.

4. SIMULATION RESULTS

The realization of the simulations, the kinematic and the dynamic models described in [20] are used. The reference trajectory is a straight line with initial coordinates $(1,2)$ and orientation of 26.56° , respectively. The initial position of the robot is $[x_0, y_0, \theta_0] = [2, 1, 10^\circ]$. The design parameters of PNC (KNC plus TNC) are chosen as: KNC $\rightarrow k_1 = 1, k_2 = 3, k_3 = 2, \gamma = 5$, and $\sigma = 2$; TNC \rightarrow DNC: $\Lambda = \text{diag}[2], \Gamma_k = 0.1, \sigma = 10$, and RNC:

$\Gamma_{pk} = 0.1$, $\sigma_p = 10$, $Q = \text{diag}[1]$. A Coulomb friction and a bounded periodic disturbance terms are added to the robot system as:

$$\bar{F} = [f_1 + f_1(t)\text{sgn}(v_1) + 0.1\sin(2\pi t) \quad (f_2 + f_2(t)\text{sgn}(v_2) + 0.1\cos(2\pi t))\bar{F}]$$

where $f_1 = 1.0$, $f_2 = 1.0$. Function $f(t)$ is nonlinear, defined as: $[f_1(t) \quad f_2(t)] = [0.0 \quad 0.0]$ if $t < 3$; $[f_1(t) \quad f_2(t)] = [0.0 \quad 5.0]$ if $3 \leq t < 8$; $[f_1(t) \quad f_2(t)] = [2.0 \quad 5.0]$ if $t \geq 8$, respectively. Thus, disturbance is subject to a sudden change at time goes to 3s and 8s. Moreover, in 8s, the mobile robot suddenly dropped of an object of 30.0kg, that is, the half of its original mass.

For this case, the simulations results are obtained of the proposed kinematic neural - (21), and (26) - and torque neural - (31), (33), and (35) - control algorithms. Also, in the KNC, DNC, and RNC of the PNC, the number of hidden neuron is 20, 20, 50 respectively. For simplicity, the centers m of the localized Gaussian Gaussian radial basis functions are evenly distributed in order to span the input space of the network. The weights of the neural networks were all unknown, assuming no knowledge about the system. It is important to emphasize that different tracking performance can be achieved by adjusting parameters gains, and others factors, such as the size of the RBFNN, centers and variances of Gaussian radial basis functions.

The tracking performance of the PNC controller can be observed in the Fig. 4.1, since the mobile robot naturally describes a smooth path tracking over the straight line, the Fig. 4.2 that the tracking errors tend to zero, and the Figs. 4.3-4.4 that the velocities tend to desired values.

Observing the Fig. 4.5, the control torques try to compensate all parametric and nonparametric uncertainties, and converge to constant value in the steady state. Also, is important to emphasize that the PNC eliminate entirely the chattering.

When abrupt changes (\bar{F} and payload) occur is observed that the tracking errors tend to zero (Fig. 4.2), because the PNC is able to compensate the abrupt changes in the mobile robot kinematics and dynamics through RBFNN learning mechanism.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A neural control algorithm (PNC) considering uncertainties in both kinematics and dynamics was proposed in this work, and can be used as an alternative trajectory tracking problem applied to nonholonomic mobile robot.

The implementation of the PNC (KNC and TNC) is based on the partitioning of neural networks into several smaller neural subnets, in order to obtain more efficient computation. This implementation simplifies the design; gives added controller structure; and

contribute to faster weight tuning algorithms (i. e., individual partitioned neural networks can be separately tuned). Another advantage of this partitioned neural networks is that if some terms in the mobile robots kinematics and dynamics are well-known (e.g., inertia matrix $\bar{H}(q)$), then their neural networks can be replaced by deterministic equations. These neural networks can be used to reconstruct only the unknown terms or those too complicated to be computed, which will probably include the friction $\bar{F}(v)$ and the Coriolis/centripetal terms $\bar{C}(q, \dot{q})$.

The RBFNN's used in the PNC neither requires an off-line learning nor the knowledge of the mobile robot kinematics and dynamics. A neural sliding mode controller as RNC of the TNC is used in the replacement of the discontinuous parts of the classical sliding mode controller to avoid the chattering as well as to suppress the neural network modeling errors, bounded unknown disturbances, influence of payload, and unknown kinematic parameters.

Stability and convergence of the robot control system, and the learning algorithms for weights are proved by using Lyapunov theory. The simulation results show the effectiveness of the PNC.

Fig. 4.1. Reference trajectory and actual trajectory using PNC.

Fig. 4.2. Tracking errors using PNC.

Fig. 4.3. Linear and angular velocities of the mobile robot using PNC.

Fig. 4.4. Angular velocities of the wheels using PNC.

Fig. 4.5. Control torques using PNC.

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